

Synergistic effects of UV-A lighting and feeding synchronization on microbial ecology, welfare, and productivity in broiler parent stock: Implications for sustainable Bio-Management

Muhammad Waqas¹, Muhammad Shabir Shaheen^{1*}, Shahid Mehmood¹, Arshad Javid²

¹Department of Poultry Production, University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Lahore, Pakistan.

²Department of Wildlife and Ecology, University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Lahore, Pakistan.

*Email: shabir.shaheen@uvas.edu.pk

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Abstract

Maintaining the health of domesticated avian species is a critical component of agricultural biodiversity and ecosystem biosecurity. This study investigated the interaction between ultraviolet-A (UV-A) lighting and feeding systems on the performance and microbial load of Ross-308 parent broilers. In a controlled trial involving 2,880 birds, we applied six lighting combinations—varying spectrum (visible, special visible, and UV-A added) and color temperature (3000K/4500K)—across two feeding systems (automatic vs. manual). Parameters included reproductive performance, welfare indicators (dust bathing, litter moisture), and the prevalence of *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. UV-A spectrum integration significantly enhanced egg production ($p \leq 0.01$) and improved welfare-related behaviors such as dust bathing ($p \leq 0.05$). Importantly, UV-A showed it can kill germs, greatly lowering the numbers of *E. coli* and *S. aureus* on bird feathers and equipment ($p \leq 0.01$). Automatic feeding further synchronized these benefits by reducing litter moisture and bird stress. The findings suggest that mimicking natural light spectrums (including UV-A) promotes the physiological well-being of domesticated birds. By reducing microbial pathogens within farm environments, these practices enhance farm biosecurity, reduce the need for pharmaceutical interventions, and minimize the ecological footprint of poultry farming, thereby supporting the conservation of healthier agricultural landscapes. The impact of UV light inside a poultry house may further reduce the risk of pathogen spillover into local ecosystems.

Keywords: Ultraviolet spectrum; automatic feeding; egg production

Introduction

Lighting and feed management are determining factors in the productive and reproductive performance of commercial broiler parent stocks. The feeding program, which encompasses quantity and quality, regulates weight, body structure, and health, being especially critical in

parent stocks, which have defined weekly goals (Laraib et al., 2021). With feed accounting for a substantial portion of production costs (around 75%), efficiency in its use is paramount. Automatic feeding systems allow for more accurate distribution, significantly reducing the waste observed in manual methods (Mustafa et al., 2021). The interdependence between sexual maturity, body weight, and growth emphasizes the need for accurate feeding schedules, making automatic feeding a superior option to manual feeding, which carries greater risks of waste and uneven distribution. Once parent stocks reach the target body weight for males and females (around 147 days), they are given a specific lighting program in duration and intensity to stimulate the maturation of their reproductive system (Sadaf et al., 2021; Erensoy et al., 2021). Therefore, two key factors that play a vital role in achieving sexual maturity, i.e., one is body weight and the second is light. Light intensity and duration simply provoke the hormonal physiology to excel the birds in the production phase, also termed “photo-stimulation” (Sun et al., 2023; Hussain et al., 2025). A comprehensive lighting program must be adopted to synchronize the flock's performance after achieving a uniform body weight. The intensity and duration of the light act as signals that trigger hormonal changes, propelling the birds towards the production phase (Afrouziyeh et al., 2021; Noor et al., 2021). To optimize and synchronize the performance of the flock after reaching a uniform body weight, it is crucial to implement a comprehensive lighting program. Light could influence the performance and welfare of parent stocks in a variety of ways. Their qualities, such as intensity, duration, spectrum, flicker frequency, and color temperature, have effects on both individuals and collectively in birds (Khan et al., 2014; Mohammed, 2019; Hussain et al., 2025). Light perception in poultry is remarkably diverse due to its unique visual physiology. For example, the presence of an additional photoreceptor cone allows chickens to perceive both the visible and ultraviolet spectrums (Seifert et al., 2020; Khalid et al., 2023).

The ultraviolet-A portion of the light spectrum usually ranges from 320nm to 400nm (Kämmerling et al., 2017; Masood et al., 2021). It has a vital role in recognizing invisible patterns, i.e., plumage patterns of the mates, which is used for social hierarchy and partner selection (Wichman et al., 2021; Vasdal et al., 2023). In addition, ultraviolet A (UVA) radiation could sexually stimulate birds, which would influence the reproductive performance of breeding stock during the production phase (Ali et al., 2018; Rana & Campbell, 2021). On the other hand, in vivo studies suggest positive effects of UVA on various species of *E. coli* and *Staphylococcus* (Ali et al., 2017; Rezaie et al., 2020). Investigating this effect in live birds and equipment within poultry houses could be a novel approach. ‘Light color temperature’ is another important influencing factor for birds. Traditionally, cool white light is preferred for the breeding phase, as it promotes melatonin production. In contrast, warm white light is considered more suitable for stimulating the

reproductive tract of breeding birds during the production phase (Hussian et al., 2025). While warm light is also associated with increased egg production (Zaguri et al., 2020), the combined effect of light temperature and its spectrum has yet to be thoroughly investigated in commercial poultry farming.

In the wild, the above-mentioned components of light are part of a chicken's natural habitat as compared to intensive systems of poultry production. Absence of any component of light not only disrupts the natural vision of chickens but also the microbial content inside the intensive system of rearing. Naturally, such microbial flora on the ground and in the surroundings are maintained due to the presence of UV components. However, inside the poultry house, the composition and quantity of such flora may be more widespread compared to the wild. The adoption of new lighting regimes and automatic feeding systems in commercial poultry farming led to the hypothesis that these would be more beneficial to birds than conventional methods. Therefore, the present study aimed to comparatively evaluate various lighting and feeding regimes in PS broilers at a commercial level, examining their effects on growth and welfare during the rearing phase.

Materials and methods

Housing and Design of Experiment

This study was conducted at a commercial broiler PS farm located at geographic coordinates [30.742N, 73.514E]. The main objective was to investigate the synergism between lighting and power systems. To carry out this research, two houses within the same poultry farm were selected, each equipped with a different feeding system: automatic feeding and manual feeding.

Each house was divided into six experimental groups to apply six different combinations of illumination, resulting from the combination of three light spectrums and two light color temperatures. The light spectrums used were as follows:

- 1) Visible spectrum [400-700nm wavelength]: conventional light-emitting diode (LED) bulbs available in the market were used for this purpose.
- 2) Special visible spectrum [400-700nm wavelength]: specially designed lamps for poultry were used for this purpose.
- 3) Ultraviolet-A added visible [320-700nm wavelength]: the lamps that emit both visible and ultraviolet-A portions of the spectrum were used for this purpose.

In addition to the three light spectrums, two color temperatures were employed for each spectrum: warm white (3000 Kelvin) and cool white (4500 Kelvin). In this way, a total of 12 treatment combinations were generated [3 spectrums × 2 color temperatures × 2 feeding systems] (**Error! Reference source not found.**).

Table 1. Layout of the design of experiment: interaction of 3 light spectrums and 2 light color temperatures with 2 feeding systems.

Sr. No.	Treatments	Replication
1.	Visible warm white + auto feeding	Treatment combinations = 12 Replicate of each combination = 6 Birds per replicate = 40 Total birds = 12 × 6 × 40 = 2,880
2.	Visible warm white + manual feeding	
3.	Visible cool white + auto feeding	
4.	Visible cool white + manual feeding	
5.	Special visible warm white + auto feeding	
6.	Special visible warm white + manual feeding	
7.	Special visible cool white + auto feeding	
8.	Special visible cool white + manual feeding	
9.	UVA added visible warm white + auto feeding	
10.	UVA added visible warm white + manual feeding	
11.	UVA added visible cool white + auto feeding	
12.	UVA added visible cool white + manual feeding	

To prevent light interference between the different treatments, the replicates were designed with isolation measures (Fig. 1). A total of 2,880 broiler breeding birds (♀) of Ross-308 strain were randomly selected at the age of one day. From these birds, 40 chicks were randomly allocated to each replicate and reared for the first 24 weeks of age (rearing phase) and then for another 24 weeks (production phase). The rest of the management practices detailed in the Ross-308 Parent Stock Management Guide were strictly followed (Aviagen, 2023; Hussain et al., 2023).

Figure 1. Design of a single poultry house with replication; 36 replicas in a chicken coop (with a feeding system). **VW:** visible warm white; **VC:** visible cold white; **SW:** special visible warm white; **SC:** special visible cold white; **UW:** UVA added warm white; **UC:** UVA added cool white; **Yellow:** The aftershocks indicate warm white; **Blue:** The aftershocks indicate cold weather.

Microbial Analysis

Swab sampling of 9 hens per replicate was randomly performed to measure the impact of light on surface sanitation. The samples were taken from the three surfaces [3 samples from each surface]: litter, bird's plumage, and equipment. Samples were taken at 25th, 36th, and 48th weeks of age and sent to the nearest lab for testing growth and count of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. MacConkey Agar was used for *E. coli*, and Mannitol Salt Agar for Staph growth. In the case of colony count, Nutrient Agar was used, which is not selective in growth. To perform the total colony count, cultures were transferred from swab samples into liquid medium [phosphate-buffered saline], diluted, and plated for enumerations. The original data were not log-transformed and analyzed as such.

Production and Welfare Parameters

Egg Production. Eggs were collected 6 times a day. Total daily eggs were divided by the number of hens on that day, multiplied by 100 to get hen-day production %. As Ross-308 normally reaches peak production at the 31st week of age, hen-week production % of each replicate was noted at this age as peak production. Similarly, the cumulative number of eggs was noted for each pen until the end of the trial period and divided by the number of hens housed to get total eggs per bird per hen-housed (Aviagen, 2023).

Dust Bathing. This parameter was noted once every 2 weeks, starting from 3rd week of age. For this purpose, birds were observed after 6 hours of feeding for 10 minutes from each replicate. For dust bathing, the sitting position of birds in the litter with the use of the wings, head, neck, and legs was observed (Liu *et al.*, 2020; Khalid *et al.*, 2023).

Litter Moisture. Litter samples were taken from 3 different places of a replicate, 3 times during the production phase: at 25th, 36th, and 48th weeks. The moisture level was estimated after drying a 100g sample on a heating plate at 70 °C for 3 hours. To get the moisture percentage, dried sample weight was subtracted from the moist litter weight and then divided by the original moist litter sample weight, multiplied by 100. The average litter moisture for each replicate was calculated using the arithmetic mean formula.

Statistical Analysis

The light spectrum, color temperature, and feeding system were taken as independent variables, while microbial production and welfare parameters were taken as dependent variables. The platform of IBM SPSS Statistics (version 27) analytical software was used for analysis. Parameters were analyzed through General Linear Model (GLM) while alpha was set at 95% level of

significance. In addition to this, Duncan's Multiple Range (DMR) as a post hoc test was applied to estimate the significant treatment combination(s) (Duncan, 1955). To check the interaction effect, the variables were decoded and converted into a one-way ANOVA, and then a post-hoc test was applied. Furthermore, the Chi-Square Test of Independence was used to find significant growth of bacteria [in terms of 'growth' and 'no growth']. The total count was analyzed using the GLM method. The following mathematical model was adopted for this study:

$$Y_{ijkl} = \mu + \alpha_i + \beta_j + \gamma_k + (\alpha \times \beta)_{ij} + (\alpha \times \gamma)_{ik} + (\beta \times \gamma)_{jk} + \epsilon_{ijkl}$$

- Y_{ijkl} = observation of dependent variables due to i, j and k treatment groups.
- μ = general population means
- α_i = effect of i^{th} light spectrum ($i = 1, 2, 3$)
- β_j = effect of j^{th} light color temperature ($j = 1, 2$)
- γ_k = effect of k^{th} feeding system ($k = 1, 2$)
- ϵ_{ijkl} = residual effect associated with treatment groups.

Results

Microbial Analysis

The light spectrum in the UV region is considered to have germicidal effect, so this impact was recorded to check the growth of *E coli* (Table 2) and *Staphylococcus (Staph) aureus* (Table 3. **Error! Reference source not found.**). According to findings, bacterial growth was significantly reduced ($P < 0.001$) under the UVA light spectrum. As swab samples showed significantly less microbial growth, which were taken under the UVA light spectrum. While no such effect could be recorded on the visible and special visible spectrum. Based on findings of microbial growth, a highly significant reduction in count [$F(2,71) = 40.50, P < 0.001$] was observed owing to the light spectrum. The trend of bactericidal activity was such that significantly fewer colonies of bacteria could be recorded under UVA light spectrum (Figure 1.2). While visible and special visible spectrums did not influence the total colony count.

Table 2. Effect of light spectrum on the growth of *E coli* from different surfaces in a poultry house.

<i>Escherichia coli</i>		Light Spectrum			Total	P-value
		Visible	Special visible	UVA + visible		
Growth from bird's plumage						
Absence	Count	4 ^b	4 ^b	27 ^a	35	<0.001
	Percentage	11.4%	11.4%	77.1%	100%	
Growth from equipment						
Absence	Count	5 ^b	4 ^b	14 ^a	23	0.015
	Percentage	21.7%	17.4%	60.9%	100%	
Growth from litter surface						
Absence	Count	4 ^b	3 ^b	17 ^a	24	<0.001
	Percentage	16.7%	12.5%	70.8%	100%	

Table 3. Effect of light spectrum on the growth of *Staph aureus* from different surfaces in a poultry house.

<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>		Light Spectrum			Total	P-value
		Visible	Special visible	UVA + visible		
Growth from bird's plumage						
Absence	Count	6	9	23	38	0.001
	Percentage	15.8%	23.7%	60.5%	100%	
Growth from equipment						
Absence	Count	6	7	36	49	<0.001
	Percentage	12.2%	14.3%	73.5%	100%	
Growth from litter surface						
Absence	Count	3	4	10	17	0.072
	Percentage	17.6%	23.5%	58.8%	100%	

Figure 2.2 Total colony count of bacteria under the influence of 3 light spectrums.

Egg Production

Producing a higher number of eggs is the utmost objective of any PS farming. As expected, the light spectrum significantly influenced the peak egg production ($P < 0.001$) In such a way that the highest peak production was noted under UVA light spectrum, while comparable peak production was found between visible and special visible spectrum (Table 4). Similarly, the feed system also significantly influenced the peak production ($P = 0.001$) Higher peak production was observed in birds kept on an auto-feeding system. Likewise, color temperature also significantly influenced ($P = 0.042$) The peak as a higher peak was observed under warm white light. In addition to this, the interaction effect of light spectrum and feeding system was also found to be highly significant ($P < 0.001$) The trend of peak egg production was such that a higher peak was observed under UVA light with an auto-feeding system. In the same way, the trend of total eggs per hen-housed was almost at the pattern of peak egg production (Table 4).

Table 4. Effect of lighting and feeding system on uniformity and egg production in broiler parent stock.

Treatments		Total Egg per Hen-housed %	Peak Production %
Light Spectrum (LS)	Visible	117.17 ± 1.23 ^b	80.96 ± 1.06 ^b
	Special visible	117.85 ± 1.20 ^b	81.45 ± 0.94 ^b
	UVA + visible	119.69 ± 1.80 ^a	83.07 ± 1.49 ^a
Light color temperature (LCT)	Warm white	118.52 ± 1.62 ^a	82.05 ± 1.33 ^a
	Cool white	117.94 ± 1.90 ^b	81.60 ± 1.61 ^b
Feeding system (FS)	Auto	118.72 ± 2.14 ^a	82.20 ± 1.80 ^a
	Manual	117.75 ± 1.15 ^b	81.45 ± 0.95 ^b
Test statistics (df, F-ratio, P-value)	LS	$F(2, 72) = 33.06, P < 0.001$	$F(2, 72) = 34.36, P < 0.001$
	FS	$F(1, 72) = 13.84, P < 0.001$	$F(1, 72) = 11.97, P = 0.001$
	LCT	$F(1, 72) = 4.89, P = 0.031$	$F(1, 72) = 4.33, P = 0.042$
	LS × FS	$F(2, 72) = 14.34, P < 0.001$	$F(2, 72) = 15.94, P < 0.001$
	LS × LCT	$F(2, 72) = 1.50, P = 0.230$	$F(2, 72) = 1.37, P = 0.262$
	FS × LCT	$F(2, 72) = 1.68, P = 0.200$	$F(2, 72) = 1.35, P = 0.250$

Different superscripts on means within a column differ significantly among treatment groups at $p \leq 0.05$.

Welfare Parameters

The dust bathing activity is largely considered a playful activity and a comfort behavior. This parameter was noted to test whether said treatments provide such comfort. As far as the results of this study are concerned, there was a significant impact of the light spectrum. Whereas significantly higher dust bathing activity ($P < 0.001$) was recorded under UV-A light compared to the other spectrum (Table 5). While no effect on dust bathing was recorded under different light color temperatures. Similarly, the trend of dust bathing across the feeding system was such that significantly higher dust bathing time ($P < 0.001$) was recorded in auto feeding replicates

compared to the replicates with manual feeding. In addition to this, the interaction of the spectrum and the feeding system was also found to be highly significant ($P = 0.001$) which produced a synergistic effect on dust bathing time, *i.e.*, higher dust bathing time was found under UVA light with the auto-feeding system.

Litter moisture is an important housing parameter that may affect several comfort behaviors, such as dust bathing, foraging, sitting, etc. As the results indicate (Table 5), litter moisture was significantly affected by the spectrum and the feeding system. Specifically, significantly lower ($P < 0.001$) Litter moisture was observed under the UVA spectrum compared to other spectrums. Similarly, less litter moisture was recorded in auto feeding replicates compared to manual feeding. Surprisingly, the interaction of the feeding system and color temperature was also found to be significant ($P = 0.034$) Comparatively lower litter moisture was recorded under warm white light with the auto-feeding system.

Table 5. Effect of lighting and feeding systems on welfare parameters in broiler parent stock

Treatments		Dust Bathing (minutes)	Litter Moisture %
Light spectrum (LS)	Visible	21.29 ± 3.50 ^b	20.46 ± 3.48 ^a
	Special visible	21.22 ± 3.47 ^b	21.21 ± 3.64 ^a
	UVA + visible	24.22 ± 5.81 ^a	17.73 ± 3.85 ^b
Light color Temperature (LCT)	Warm white	22.29 ± 4.93	19.70 ± 4.18
	Cool white	22.18 ± 4.22	19.91 ± 3.67
Feeding system (FS)	Auto	25.72 ± 3.40 ^a	16.69 ± 2.66 ^b
	Manual	18.75 ± 2.38 ^b	22.91 ± 3.91 ^b
Test statistics (df, F-ratio, P-value)	LS	$F(2, 72) = 11.83, P < 0.001$	$F(2, 72) = 26.58, P < 0.001$
	FS	$F(1, 72) = 146.84, P < 0.001$	$F(1, 72) = 229.64, P < 0.001$
	LCT	$F(1, 72) = 0.03, P = 0.859$	$F(1, 72) = 0.26, P = 0.609$
	LS × FS	$F(2, 72) = 7.79, P = 0.001$	$F(2, 72) = 0.86, P = 0.427$
	LS × LCT	$F(2, 72) = 0.34, P = 0.695$	$F(2, 72) = 1.23, P = 0.299$
	FS × LCT	$F(2, 72) = 1.33, P = 0.253$	$F(2, 72) = 4.68, P = 0.034$

Different superscripts on means within a column differ significantly among treatment groups at $p \leq 0.05$.

Discussion

This study was conducted to analyze the effect of different lighting combinations (spectrum and color temperature) along with two feeding systems on the performance of broiler parent stock (PS) in commercial conditions during the phase. The productionAs expected, the growth was affected by the feeding system, while some of the welfare aspects were also found to be better under UV-A spectrum, particularly along with the auto-feeding house. Similarly, bacterial growth under UV-A spectrum was reduced as compared to other lighting regimens.

The findings of reduced bacterial growth demonstrate the hygienic impact of ultraviolet-A light on the health of poultry birds and the poultry house environment. Such findings substantiate the

germicidal effect of ultraviolet-A radiation within poultry houses as well (Li et al., 2010). Similarly, the reduction in *Staphylococcus* growth from birds' plumage under ultraviolet-A spectrum supports the *in vivo* findings of Rezaie et al. (2020). Nonetheless, this effect could not be validated in samples taken from the surface of litter and equipment. Because continuous availability of growth media on these surfaces might have reduced the impact of ultraviolet light on bacterial growth. That is why further investigations during the production phase are needed when higher light intensity is employed. In addition to this, the impact of ultraviolet-A spectrum on reduced count further asserts the beneficial impact of such spectra in poultry houses. This was supposed to be a novel in the sense that the impact of ultraviolet-A light was assessed on living poultry birds. The positive impact of ultraviolet-A light on the reduction of viable counts and colonies of germs has already been established on chicken meat (Soro et al., 2021). Furthermore, such a decrease in microbial load is also beneficial for the surrounding environment of poultry houses and nearby wildlife. The reduced germ load of existing air can reduce air pollution by a significant amount. Similarly, during cleaning and washing of poultry houses, the UVA-treated manure will help reduce seepage of contaminated water into the soil and further reduce the germ load of soil where manure could be used as fertilizer. Thus, helping reduce microbial load in the wild. Since UV-A has lower energy than UV-C, the study emphasizes that the effect is likely due to long-term exposure and oxidative stress on the bacterial membranes.

In the case of welfare, higher dust bathing of pullets under UV-A spectrum endorsed the comfort behavior associated with UV lamps (Vasdal et al., 2023). Contrarily, Rana et al. (2021) found non-significant findings on such behaviors during their study. However, the synergistic effect of auto-feeding with UV-A spectrum may have improved dust bathing behavior in the current study. As litter condition in auto feeding replicates was found superior. Because friable litter in poultry houses encourages the playful litter activity of birds, this could have improved the dust bathing activity along with the spectrum effect (Pepper & Dunlop, 2021). Moreover, the comfort behavior of experimental birds stimulated by the UV spectrum has also been endorsed in a hematological study rather than visual inspections (Sobotik et al., 2020).

Livability rates were noted for the sake of understanding the effect of UVA spectrum on peck-related mortality in broiler PS. As expected, a better livability rate in the auto-feeding house was the added advantage of a power-driven chain feeding system. The feed distribution staff often run over birds in a manually feeding system, leading to increased culling and mortality. Furthermore, comparable livability rates of pullets under different spectrums proved no correlation between UVA spectrum and mortality (Lewis et al., 2007). Moreover, UVA light is not associated with

peck-related illness and further validates its safe side for poultry houses (Vasdal et al., 2023; Wichman et al., 2021).

It was expected that the uniform distribution of feed through the automatic feeding system and perception of UVA light might hyper-stimulate the reproductive physiology of the hen, resulting in higher egg production. Surprisingly, no treatment or treatment combination affected the egg production. Specifically, UVA spectrum produced comparable egg production to the other spectrums (Spindler et al., 2020; England and Ruhnke, 2020). However, there is strong evidence that UV exposure may improve post-peak egg production and the persistence of the laying rate (Wei et al., 2020). Nevertheless, the current study spanned 25-48 weeks of age; further study is needed to confirm such a claim. In addition to the effect of spectrum, color temperature does influence the overall perception and absorption of the light waves. With longer waves, warm white light contains more of the red wavelength, which can deeply penetrate into the retina. Such hyper-stimulation because of warm white light is also associated with better egg production (Zaguri et al., 2020).

One of the important housing parameters for PS farming is litter moisture. Being a multifactor aspect, it depends on ventilation rate, litter depth, housing design, birds' density and spatial distribution, etc. (Pepper & Dunlop, 2021). However, one major aspect that can affect the litter moisture is the birds' distribution throughout the house. It was observed during visits in manual feeding house that hens tend to crowd around the entrance 1 hour before and 1 hour after feed-charge time. Such crowding might have resulted in caked litter. Because birds had developed a time-habit to remain close to the door of the replicate during the feeding period. Conversely, in an auto-feeding house, hens were spread uniformly within each replicate all the time. More uniform spreading of hens might have resulted in lower litter moisture, preventing cake formation. Furthermore, litter turning is a common practice at poultry farms to reduce litter moisture (Pepper & Dunlop, 2021; Mushtaq et al., 2021). Naturally, such practice is performed through dust bathing by hens. Interestingly, higher dust bathing activity of hens under UVA light with auto feeding house might have aided in the reduction of litter moisture as well.

Conclusion

The lighting combination of warm white with an ultraviolet spectrum has produced better findings. Similarly, when compared, the automatic feeding system is more efficient regarding uniform feed distribution and welfare aspects, e.g., improved litter moisture and dust bathing activity. In general, it is concluded that warm white color temperature of dimmable modern lamps [emitting UV-A spectrum] with an automatic feeding system is a better combination for the production phase of broiler PS birds as compared to visible spectrum with manual feeding.

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